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The effect of variability of practice on the performance and learning of coordinated coincident Task

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is investigation of the Effect of variability of practice on performance and learning coordinated-coincident task. For this reason, 24 physical education and sport science students, that mean ages of them were between 20 to 25 years old, selected with nonrandom manner. Then, they were divided to constant and variable practice groups with random manner. Practice protocol were 90 practice trials (6 block of 15 trials) with feedback in first day as acquisition phase trials through bimanual coordination tools (reliability and validity already was reported by Bahram and Shafizade) and then 15 trials without feedback as retention phase trials in 24 hours later. Data analysis displayed that constant and variable practice had no effect on performance and learning of relative phase (index of GMP) but constant practice was more benefit than variable practice on performance and learning of total timing error (index of parameter) ($p \leq 0.05$) and it had the less total timing error in each of two phases. Generally, findings of this research did not support from Schmidt's schema theory and show that variable practice has only effect on parameter but not has effect on Generalized Motor Program. Finally, according to this research finding, it is suggested that, constant practice should be used for parameterization of relatively complex tasks.

Key words: variability of practice, bimanual coordination, coordinated-coincident task.

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